

AN OLD KINGDOM OBELISK OF KHENU IN THE EGYPTIAN MUSEUM

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Abstract. *Publication of an old Kingdom Obelisk with a separate base recessed for offerings in the Egyptian Museum (formerly Cairo Museum CG 17006=JE 53677-8), including comments on the style, iconography, paleography, and dating criteria. It was discovered in the archaeological excavation season of 1921–1922, at Saqqara in the northern necropolis of the pyramid of Teti, rubble above the serdab of Khenu alias Them, near the mastaba of Mereruka. It belongs to the end of the 5th dynasty and the beginning of the 6th dynasty of the old kingdom. Although it bears no royal name, it has the style of the inscriptions that existed at the end of the old kingdom.*

Keywords: *Obelisk, Pyramidion, Limestone, Old kingdom, Saqqara, Cairo Museum, Lector Priest, Sole Companion, Osiris, Anubis, Khenu.*

INTRODUCTION

Among the collections of the Egyptian Museum is a collection of obelisks. Obelisk CG 17006 caught my eye when I saw it for the first time because it has a separate base recessed for offerings. It is a rare occurrence for this architectural element to appear specifically with inscriptions on the base of offering-basin. As well as the significant role of the obelisk, which is considered one of the oldest forms of symbolic architecture in ancient Egypt, it plays an important role in Egyptian temples, and in the Fifth Dynasty, it became the true symbol of the sun god “Ra” in the Sun Temple in Abu Sir. When the rays of the sun fell on the top of this obelisk covered with a thin layer of gold, it reflected its rays and made it glow like the sun, which led to the belief that the obelisk itself was the residence of God, his center, and even his sacred symbol. It was erected in front of the pylons of Egyptian temples and played a symbolic and celebratory role in the rising of the god his templeⁱ. The current condition of this object in comparison with the black-and-white photographs taken at the time of its discovery shows no change. but a close study of its stylistic traits is helpful to determine its artistic origin and date. Charles Kuentz transcribed the hieroglyphs of this object and included its images, but he did not translate their texts or investigate its style or inscriptionsⁱⁱ. The aim of this paper is to translate and comment on this document by investigating its style, inscriptions, iconographic and epigraphical features, and dating criteria. The importance of this object, above all, is that it records the most important titles of the old kingdom individuals on Egyptian monuments. It records the significant title of Khenu alias Them.

General description

The object is made of limestone, with no traces of color and consists of two parts. The first part is the upper part, which is the obelisk. Its height is so taller than it’s wide; measuring 60 cm in height, the width and the thickness vary between 12 cm and 13.7 cm. The second part is the lower part, which is the base, measuring 33.5 cm in height, 16 cm in width, and 9 cm in thickness. It is in good condition with fairly good preservation. It fractured into two pieces, and the tip is gone, otherwise, it is fairly good. The inscriptions on it were incised in Sunk-reliefⁱⁱⁱ.

Figure (1) Shows an image of an obelisk with a separate base in the Cairo Museum CG 17006

CHARACTERISTICS

1-The obelisk

The section is of the square type, but the faces do not have the same width, and the angles are not right. The inequality in width of the faces is the same at the top and the bottom ($4 > 2 > 1 > 3$). The faces, except face 4, are slightly convex in the horizontal section, especially in their upper part. The faces of the pyramidion are slightly convex in the vertical section. The Shaft and pyramidion are connected by a curve.

The ratio of length of the pyramidion side that represents the upper part of the obelisk on faces 1 and 3 is 14 cm, while the length of the pyramidion side of faces 2 and 4 is 13 cm. The ratio width of the base of the pyramidion, which forms the upper part of the column on face 1 is 12.5 cm, on face 2 (12.7 cm), on face 3 (12 cm), and on face 4 (12.8 cm), while the width of the base of the pyramidion on face 1 is (13.2 cm), on face 2 (13.5 cm), on face 3 (12.9 cm), and on face 4 (13.7 cm) ^{iv}.

Figure (2) a- Shows measurements of the obelisk

b- Shows section measurements below the pyramidion

c- Shows section measurements above the base

II. The Pedestal

The base is barely roughed out from below; it must have been plunged half into the ground. At one end of the upper surface is the place of the obelisk; at the other end is a small pool. As both objects were not found in situ, it is difficult to say how the obelisk was oriented on its base. According to the inscriptions, it is likely that the base was placed transversely to the axis of the tomb and that the inscribed face (face 2) of the obelisk was parallel to one of the long sides. The ratio of length dimensions of the separated base is on faces 1 (16 cm), 2 (33.5 cm), 3 (15.5 cm), and 4 (33 cm). The average thickness of the base is 9 cm, while the depth of the engraved part in the separated base designated for installing the obelisk shaft is 2.2 cm

Figure (3) a- Shows measurements of the base

*b- Shows the base thickness and the depth of the hole
 in which the obelisk is installed.*

The inscriptions on this archaeological object were carried out on the obelisk and on the separate base, as shown in the diagram below. The inscriptions for the supposed respective positions of the obelisk and the base are divided into:

**Figure (4) Supposed
 respective position of the
 obelisk and the base.**

I- The obelisk

The obelisk was framed by a line on all four sides. It bears on side 2 a column of hieroglyphs framed by a line starting at 2 cm, approximately below the pyramidion, and it can be displayed as a picture and a facsimile as follows:

Figure (5) a- Shows an image of the obelisk

b- Shows Facsimile of the text on side 2

smr waty^(a) Xry- Hb^(b) imAxw^(c) xr Wsir^(d) xnw

The Sole Companion, the Lector Priest, and the one venerated before Osir, Khenu.

REMARKS ON THE TEXT AND COMMENTARY

^A At the beginning of the vertical line of the obelisk's main inscription, before the name of the obelisk's owner, the title of the sole companion appears. The title smr- waty is a high honorific title ^{vi}. It is the commonest title of the courtiers and it was given to the most one close to the king ^{vii}. In addition, it indicates the privileged status to his owner for the king. Moreover, it was common in the texts of high rank officials of the old kingdom ^{viii}. The common translation of this title is 'sole companion' ^{ix}. The title smr waty was inscribed with vertical stick. When the scribe

wants to write smr only he writes it with the determinative (A345) ^x. While he wants to write smr waty he writes the vertical stick instead of the determinative. For Old Kingdom examples see: stela of Khnumhotpe (British Museum EA1166, Fifth Dynasty) ^{xi}, the inscriptions of Tjetu I (Giza G.2001, late the Sixth Dynasty) ^{xii}, the false doors of Khentyka ^{xiii}, false door (Copenhagen National Museum 5129) ^{xiv}, the stela of Weni ^{xv}, Sixth Dynasty. False door of Qar, (British Museum EA1342, Sixth Dynasty) ^{xvi}, inscriptions of Nepepi, Abydos, reign of Merenre 1, and Mereri stela from Dendera, Seventh Dynasty ^{xvii}.

^B the second word in the compound is a feminine, Hbt means 'ritual-book', though the ending t is almost always omitted ^{xviii}. Lector priest was responsible for directing and reciting the daily rituals in the cult establishment in which he was employed. As reliefs of tombs and temples of the Old Kingdom, he

played an essential role in the funeral and temple ceremonies^{xix}. He had not only to read the texts of the rituals, but also in some ceremonies he was a kind of prayer leader. In the early times, the members of the royal family obtained this rank and office. Xry –Hb is written in the obelisk under

study without determinative^{xx}. The title Xry –Hb(t) appears as early as the Second Dynasty, usually held by the crown prince^{xxi}. It is a common title in the Old Kingdom. See for examples: Cone of Khuu(or Khuue) (British Museum EA199, Fourth or Fifth Dynasty)^{xxii}, architrave of Washptah, (British Museum EA1278, Fifth Dynasty)^{xxiii}, stela of Eni, (British Museum EA1485, Sixth Dynasty)^{xxiv}, a lintel from Qar's mastaba^{xxv}, false door of Qar, (British Museum EA1342, Sixth Dynasty)^{xxvi}, and stela of Imydepet-Bau, (British Museum EA128, Sixth Dynasty)^{xxvii}.

^C This epithet first appeared in the Second Dynasty^{xxviii}, and was attested at the beginning of the Fourth Dynasty. Its full orthography is typical of the Old Kingdom^{xxix}. This designation is popular in the offering grant **Htp-dj-njsw.t** and other text genres^{xxx}. Allen has considered it a quality of the deceased or of someone, usually the king or the great god^{xxxi}. Nevertheless, it has become clear that this epithet is not related to the fact that his or her bearer is deceased. In that respect, Jansen-Winkeln argues that this epithet could be applied to both the dead and the living^{xxxii}. Also, Chauvet, in her analysis of that epithet, assumes that his or her bearer was entailed in income during his or her lifetime. He obtains his status as **imAx** because of his achievement, moral qualities, and social prestige^{xxxiii}. Moret alludes to the economic aspect of the **jmAx**-status. Depending on the personal achievement of **jmAx.w** person, he will be qualified for royal endowments in the form of food provisions and funerary equipment^{xxxiv}. Helck underscores that this epithet is usually understood as an association entailing provision for the funerary estate by the one with whom the deceased is **jmAx.w**^{xxxv}. To sum up, the **jmAx**-status guarantees all royal endowments of food and funeral equipment after death. Also, it becomes a precondition for performing the glorification ritual for the deceased, i.e., the **sAx.w** process.

^D It is one of the rare times when the name of the god Osiris is mentioned with the determinative of the god are common in the Sixth Dynasty^{xxxvi}; for examples, see: false doors of Khentyka^{xxxvii}, (mastaba dated to the early years of Pepy I's reign)^{xxxviii}, stela of Imydepet-Bau (British Museum EA128)^{xxxix}, stela of Hynehes (Cairo CG.1695)^{xl}, inscriptions of Tjeti I (Giza G.2001, late Sixth Dynasty)^{xli}. The feature of the two connected elements of Osiris name becomes less common after the Old Kingdom, when the two signs are usually at least slightly separated^{xlii}. Kanawati has noted that from the beginning of Teti's reign a new development is observed in the inscriptions of the burial chambers and sarcophagi: the seated god determinative of Osiris is eliminated; the name being

written ^{xliii}. This feature isn't found in the obelisk under study and other inscriptions throughout the time of Sixth Dynasty as in the tombs of the vizier Neferseshemre^{xliv}, Ankhmahor^{xlv}, Mereruka, Khentika, Khentika's son, Khentika, the latter probably belonging to the reign of Pepy I^{xlvi}, and the stela of Hynehes (Cairo CG.1695, Sixth Dynasty)^{xlvii}. However, one can notice also the determinative of the god Osiris in the name Wsir is as often omitted as it is present in Sixth Dynasty inscriptions, cf. the false doors of Khentyka at Saqqara^{xlviii}, the stela of Khennu (Cairo CG.1615)^{xlix}, the stelae of Ti, Cairo CG.1590, from Abydos)¹ and Imydepet-Bau (British

Museum EA128, Sixth Dynasty)^{li}, the inscriptions of Tjetu I (Giza G.2001, late the Sixth Dynasty)^{liii}, where the determinative is present.

I- The Pedestal

The base bears between the basin and the obelisk five lines of hieroglyphs directed like this (fig.). The inscription is framed by a line on all four sides, and it can be displayed as a picture and a facsimile as follows:

Figure (6) a- Shows an image of the base

b- Shows Facsimile of the text

smr waty Xry- Hb imAxw xr Inpw^(e) tp Dw.f^(f) xnw rn.f^(g) Tmi

The Sole Companion, the Lector Priest, and the one venerated before Inpw- who-dwells upon his mountain, Khenu, his good name being Them.

REMARKS ON THE TEXT AND COMMENTARY

^E The writing of the name of Anubis with the Jackal sign on a shrine is only attested from the beginning of the Sixth Dynasty^{liii}. Anubis, who is in the divine booth, was responsible for having the deceased buried in the necropolis. Anubis was one of the gods that was always invoked in the **Htp-dj-njsw.t** formula, beginning in the Fourth Dynasty until the early Twelfth Dynasty^{liv}. By the reign of Amenemhat III, Osiris had become the most popular god, while Anubis had lost favor^{lv}.

^F tp Dw.f 'He who is on his mountain' is one of the most popular epithets of the god Anubis which was first attested, although rarely, in the offering formula from the Fifth Dynasty

^{lvi}. The arrangement of the epithet tp Dw.f appears infrequently in this form ^{lvii}. In some rare

cases, the addition of a stroke beside the Dw (N26) sign to the aforementioned arrangement appears on the stela of the Egyptian museum (Cairo JE 88011), and also on the stela of Wadj-setji from Mesheikh, which Leprohon dated to the late First Intermediate period, or the beginning of the Eleventh Dynasty ^{lviii}.

^G The standard writing for **rn** was purely alphabetic (V10) ^{lix}. During the Old Kingdom and quite often later, the personal name, supplemented with rank and title(s), was usually considered sufficient for the identification of the living and the dead. In ancient Egypt, an individual’s name was of vital importance for defining his identity in society and ensuring his survival for posterity ^{lx}. A person might have two or even three names, one of them sometimes being a basilophorous name (a name that incorporates a king’s name) adopted by the individual at a certain stage of life. In the Old Kingdom, it was common to have two names: a “major name” **rn aA**, which often was an official theophorous or basilophorous name (that is, one that included the name of a deity or king, respectively), and a “minor name” **rn nDs** or “beautiful name” **rn nfr**, which occasionally was an abbreviation of the major name and served as a first name, the term **rn nfr**, although conventionally translated “beautiful name” is perhaps rather to be understood as “final name” ^{lxi}. In the monuments, the two names are sometimes clearly separated and classified.

CONCLUSION

The importance of this article lies in the publication of an Obelisk with a separate base, which was discovered in the funerary cemetery beside Teti’s complex in Saqqara and transferred to the Egyptian Museum. It was dated to the late 5th dynasty and the beginning of the 6th dynasty of the old kingdom dynasty, because it has palaeographical and artistic features of this period. The object described in this paper was inscribed with hieroglyphic signs of the old Egyptian language in its ancient era. The text indicates the symbolic and functional meaning of the titles of the deceased and palaeographical remarks of writing, signs, and determinatives that had occurred in the text, the most important of which was the appearance of the determinative of the god in the name of Osiris, which was unusual in the texts of the Old Kingdom. As well as the appearance of the sign names of the deities Osiris and Anubis without the basic simplified offering formula **Htp-di- nsw** of the old kingdom. The first fragment of the object is the obelisk of Khenu, which demonstrates his high-ranking status from the end of the Fifth Dynasty to the middle of the Sixth Dynasty as the sole companion, the lector priest, and the one venerated before Osiris. While the second fragment of the object is the pedestal, it indicates the same previous titles in addition to another title, the one venerated before Anubis, as well as another name of the deceased, which is called Them. Finally, the object of **xnw rn.f Tmi** was, in all probability, a part of his mastaba tomb, which was located south of Mereruka mastaba beside the Pyramid of the King in the Teti Pyramid Cemetery in Saqqara.

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